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Taller XXIII d'Investigació en Filosofia

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XXIII Taller d'Investigació en Filosofia
Book of Abstracts

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Taller d'Investigació en Filosofia

TIF 2026

7–8 de maig de 2026 · Universitat de València · Sala de Junes

07 Dijous / Thursday

9:15 Indeterminacy and the Unity of Grounding and Causation

Robert Oliver

Freie Universität Berlin

COMMENTARY

Adriano Aguado Nocilla

Universitat de Barcelona

11:00 On Using AI to Know Ourselves

Diana Craciun

University College London

COMMENTARY

Alba Lavagnoli González

Universidad de Valladolid

12:45 Is Niche-Construction Necessarily Agential? The Case of Ghost Niche Construction

Alba G. Padrós

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COMMENTARY

Adex Izquierdo

Universitat de València

15:30 Modal transcendentalism without transcendental idealism?

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Universitat de València

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Iván Pazos Solla

Universitat de Barcelona

17:15 Affective Disclosure and the Roots of Epistemic Commitment: A Response to Álvarez-González's "Emotional Phenomenology: A New Puzzle"

Francesca Camilla Mattioli

Universidad de Murcia

COMMENTARY

Cathlene Cruz Centeno

Universidad Nacional de Educación a Distancia

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Omar Ruiz

University of St Andrews / University of Stirling

COMMENTARY

Paulina Kraft

Universitat de Barcelona

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Universidad de Granada

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Dani Alnashi

Università della Svizzera Italiana

COMMENTARY

Valentina Di Cataldo

Universitat d'Alacant

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Ana López Rodríguez

Universidad de Granada

COMMENTARY

Sergio Guerra

Universidad de Granada

INVITED SPEAKER

XXIII Taller d'Investigació
en Filosofia

&

Valencia Philosophy
in Colloquium

It's About Perspective: An Argument Against Relationalism

Sergio Guerra

Universidad de Granada

Abstract

The main aim of this talk is to motivate the rejection of Relationalism, the most widely accepted analysis of propositional attitude attributions. According to Relationalism, (i) attitude verbs are two-place predicates, (ii) “that”-clauses are singular terms designating propositions, and (iii) attributions are used to describe facts consisting of subjects standing in relations to propositions. The rejection of Relationalism is usually motivated on the basis of Prior’s puzzle, which shows that it is not always possible to substitute a “that”-clause for another singular term designating the same proposition while preserving the truth-conditions. However, Prior’s puzzle does not seem to provide a good motivation for rejecting Relationalism, given that the puzzle does not arise with all propositional attitude verbs and that defenders of Relationalism have offered convincing solutions to it. As an alternative strategy, I will argue that Relationalism precludes a satisfactory solution to Frege’s puzzle—that is, the problem of why it is not always possible to substitute *salva veritate* coextensional expressions within “that”-clauses. First, I will argue that Relationalism implies a particular explanation of why instances of Frege’s puzzle arise, namely that the speaker, the audience, and the subject of the attribution do not stand in the same epistemic relation to the relevant proposition or its constituents. Second, I will show that Fregeanism and Russellianism—the two main families of solutions to Frege’s puzzle—presuppose Relationalism and its way of understanding the puzzle. I will argue that, as a consequence, these approaches cannot account for cases in which the subject of the attribution knows that the substituted expressions are coextensional, such as circumstances in which evaluative expressions (e.g., slurs or deadnames) are substituted for their allegedly neutral counterparts. I propose to reject (i) and suggest a relativist alternative to Relationalism, on which attitude verbs are analyzed as circumstance-shifting operators.

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A Matter of Attitude? Two Senses of "Expressive" in Expressivism

Indeterminacy and the Unity of Grounding and Causation

Robert Oliver

Freie Universität Berlin

Abstract

This paper argues that there is grounding indeterminacy: it is sometimes indeterminate what grounds what. I develop several cases of grounding indeterminacy with different structures. In such cases, once all the relevant facts of the scenario are settled, it remains unsettled whether particular grounding relations obtain. I argue that this is a kind of worldly indeterminacy, i.e. its source does not lie in our ignorance or semantic indecision, but in reality itself, which may be indeterminate in some respects (see Barnes & Williams 2011; Wilson 2013; Wilson 2018).

Grounding is a generative priority relation that imposes a hierarchical structure on reality between the more fundamental and the less fundamental (Schnieder 2020: 107; pioneering work introducing the notion is due to Fine 2001; 2010, 2012; Rosen 2010; Schaffer 2009). It is a form of metaphysical dependence that is widely thought to share many similarities with causal dependence (Baron-Schmitt & Vogt, forthcoming; Bennett 2017; Schaffer 2016; Wilson 2018; for general criticism, see Bernstein 2016b). Building on this line of research, I argue that causation and grounding share a hitherto underexplored feature: both exhibit similar kinds of indeterminacy. I show that for each kind of indeterminacy considered in relation to causation, there is a corresponding parallel in grounding.

In saying that there is grounding indeterminacy, we may be making distinct claims that do not necessarily depend on one another. One thing we might mean is that full grounds do not metaphysically necessitate what they ground. Proponents of this view can be divided into those who defend non-probabilistic contingent grounding (Leuenberger 2014; Skiles 2015), those who argue for probabilistic grounding (Bader 2021), and those who make explicit appeal to indeterministic laws of metaphysics (Wasserman 2017). Another thing we might mean by grounding indeterminacy is that there are grounding relations that obtain between entities at least one of which is vague. For example, consider the following claims: “the fact that Rafaela is much taller than Marina is grounded in Rafaela’s and Marina’s respective heights and the ordering relation between these heights,” and “S is a member of group G by virtue of participation in the G-culture” (Richardson 2024: 40). Both the judgment about what counts as “much taller” and, in the latter case, about

whether S participates in the G-culture may be vague. Similar claims are made about causation: that it is indeterministic (see Hitchcock 2021) and that it can obtain between vague relata (Torrago 2000).

Yet another idea is that it can be indeterminate what grounds what, or whether a grounding relation holds between two facts. In recent work in the metaphysics of causation, it has been argued that sometimes it is indeterminate what causes what, or whether a causal relationship obtains between two determinate relata (Bernstein 2016a; Hoffmann-Kolss 2024; Swanson 2017). Likewise, I argue that grounding is sometimes indeterminate in this sense and, moreover, that grounding indeterminacy does not face some of the problems that causal indeterminacy does.

I present cases of grounding indeterminacy with different structures: first, cases in which all the relata determinately obtain, but the direction of grounding is indeterminate—that is, it is indeterminate what does the grounding and what is grounded. Second, cases in which it is indeterminate which of a plurality of possible grounds obtains, so it is indeterminate which particular grounding relation obtains. Among these latter cases, some are based on Sorites paradoxes for grounding that leave indeterminate what grounds what, and others involve no vagueness.

I then argue that introducing grounding indeterminacy into our metaphysical toolkit is theoretically fruitful. I do so by showing how the existence of grounding indeterminacy can best explain several relevant metaphysical scenarios and how it is compatible with well-entrenched principles of grounding.

I end by offering some remarks in defence of the view that grounding indeterminacy, like causal indeterminacy, is sometimes worldly—i.e. neither semantic nor epistemic—and by pointing to further research on related parallels between indeterminacy in the laws of nature and the laws of metaphysics, as well as between future indeterminacy and indeterminacy as to what the non-fundamental facts are.

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On Using AI to Know Ourselves

Diana Craciun

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Abstract

Humans have always used external tools to know themselves. We ask others what they think about us, we brainstorm with our therapists, we use diaries to carefully monitor trends in our thoughts, and we make inferences about ourselves from how organised our rooms are or the kinds of people we spend time with. In short, there is an established path to self-knowledge by means of external factors. At least when it comes to what Cassam (2014) calls ‘substantive self-knowledge’, i.e., knowledge of what makes us who we are, such as knowledge of our character traits, aptitudes, and values, external tools seem to have a role to play. Yet the advent of new technologies promises to take this even further. For example, Schwengerer (2023) argues that virtual reality (VR) can contribute to self-knowledge. Alternatively, there are now tools and algorithms that claim high accuracy in their observation of us. Smartwatches can tell us how good our sleep is, how healthy our lifestyles. Online algorithms can tell us what our taste in music and visual media is. Tests such as the MBTI can purportedly reveal our personalities. Our environment has moved from subtly reflecting aspects of ourselves to actively interpreting us. It no longer merely provides evidence, but rather it performs the inference. Finally, the most promising tool towards self-discovery seems to be AI. We can now have conversations with large language models (LLMs) such as ChatGPT and purportedly gain insight into ourselves in no time. We can sit back and let it interpret us—no need to self-reflect.

Some may argue that AI is a ‘hyper-learning’ tool (Glickman & Sharot, 2024), since it has the following features: i) it has a high signal-to-noise ratio, which facilitates learning, ii) it has greater data processing ability, and iii) it is perceived to have higher knowledge than humans in some domains. Presumably, then, there is an argument to be made for the following (descriptive) position:

AI-Powered Self-Knowledge: if we provide AI with enough data about ourselves, or if we allow it to observe us for long enough, it can reliably lead us to know ourselves, given its information processing abilities.

Given the rapid rise in AI capabilities, this seems plausible (if not currently, then soon). However, I draw attention to this position because it may give rise to the following prescriptive standpoint, which is much more debatable:

(Epistemic) Ought to Use AI: Since AI can reliably lead to self-knowledge, we ought to use it over more traditional and internal means of self-knowledge, such as reflecting or journaling about ourselves.

Let us say that AI-powered self-knowledge justifies *(Epistemic) Ought to use AI*, or that it at the very least justifies the following, weaker, position:

Reason to Use AI: Since AI can reliably lead to self-knowledge, we have a reason to use it towards self-knowledge.

In this paper, I argue against *(Epistemic) Ought to use AI*, and I also argue that if there is a reason to use AI, then it is a very weak one, such that in most circumstances it is defeated by reasons to not use AI. First, the framework I will use is Cassam's (2014) inferentialism. To gain substantial self-knowledge, such as knowing our character traits and values, we infer from a pool of evidence. Importantly, that inference is mediated by some theory of mind, i.e., some implicit theoretical commitment about why certain pieces of evidence contribute towards a certain conclusion. For example, we presumably have a theory of love according to which having butterflies in one's stomach counts as evidence that one is in love.

My position is that over-relying on AI and similar algorithmic tools in our inferences about ourselves is particularly problematic because it lowers our familiarity with our theories of mind, which in turn weakens our reasoning frameworks overall. When we introspect—by which I mean any kind of self-reflection, be that through internal or external monologue, or through writing—we familiarise ourselves with our point of view, our thoughts, our theories of mind, and the ways in which we reason. By outsourcing inferential work to AI or other algorithms, we become increasingly estranged from our epistemic processes, and thereby from a key aspect of who we are. We do not have a chance to employ or question our own theories of mind.

Not only that, but outsourcing self-reflection to AI also allows it to gradually alter our theories of mind. Joseph (2025) neatly summarises how the algorithms around us do not merely passively reflect aspects of ourselves, but rather actively participate in co-creating the self. This is because algorithms interpret the information they receive. A diary will not interpret the information you put in, but algorithms such as the one powering ChatGPT will interpret your input in light of their embedded theories. We therefore may end up internalising the interpretative frameworks of these algorithms, using them to interpret ourselves without realising it.

This has both practical and epistemic implications. At the practical level, a loss of familiarity with our theories of mind and reasoning process more broadly results in weakening our sense of self, and the fact that AI also subtly changes our theories of mind constitutes a threat to our authenticity. As such, insofar as we think that authenticity and having a strong sense of self are important for the good life, we should avoid relying on AI for self-knowledge.

Epistemically, the loss of familiarity with our reasoning frameworks and their gradual shift towards the AI's frameworks are problematic consequences. This is because, I suggest, being good epistemic agents requires being able to keep track of our own reasoning frameworks and being able to justify our beliefs by reference to our frameworks. If our beliefs are merely inherited from AI and not reasoned towards by us agents, then we are not going to be in a position to defend or justify our beliefs. This, I argue, is epistemically irresponsible—or vicious.

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From Environment to Phenotype: Agency and the Limits of Niche Construction

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Abstract

During recent years, agency has played an increasingly prominent role in theoretical discussions of development and evolution, particularly through Niche Construction (NC). NC refers to the ways in which organisms alter their environments, thereby influencing selective pressures and in turn leading to differential evolutionary outcomes (Odling-Smee, Laland, and Feldman 2003). In its original formulation, NC included phenomena as diverse as nest building, migration, or the emission of detritus. Unlike accounts centered on selection—in which organisms are considered passive recipients of whatever pressures they face—NC aims to highlight the active role of organisms, which may bias and shape selection.

Yet, as the concept has expanded, certain developments have led to disagreement over what should properly count as NC, and over how far it can be extended without losing its explanatory power. Such concerns are not new: from its inception, NC has been criticized for being overly comprehensive and for lacking a clear demarcation between the organism and its environment. This issue becomes particularly apparent when NC is taken to include cases of organismal activity that do not directly alter environmental factors, such as relocation (e.g., migration), tool use, or, more recently, Medial Niche Construction (Chiu 2019).

One of the most recent theoretical developments within NC has been the inclusion of changes to the organism's own phenotype as instances of Niche Construction. This was proposed by Aaby and Ramsey (2022), who coined the term *Constitutive NC*. Together with *Relational NC*—corresponding roughly to Odling-Smee et al. (2003) and to Relocational NC with certain additions—and *External NC*—corresponding to Perturbational NC—this new classification aimed to redraw the boundaries of what phenomena are considered NC.

The idea that certain developmental processes could count as NC was already present in earlier authors such as Sultan (2015) and Walsh (2015), as well as in several works by Laland (2024), which emphasized the intimate connection between development and NC.

In Aaby and Ramsey (2022), however, this inclusion was explicitly motivated by the need to render the concept of the *selective niche*—understood as the set of selective pressures faced by a population—more coherent. Since such selective pressures can change not only through modifications of environmental factors but also through changes in the organism’s body or in its relation to those factors, they argued that development itself, for instance in the case of phenotypic plasticity, should be included as NC.

In this talk, we shall argue that considering changes to the phenotype as instances of Niche Construction requires treating both development and NC as agential processes. However, this requirement, which is often left implicit, proves problematic, as it renders NC dependent on particular accounts of organismal agency and aggravates some of the issues that have been raised against it.

However, considering development as an agential process is highly controversial. In the context of development, agency is typically conceptualized as *goal-directedness*. In these accounts, goals are understood in a non-cognitive and non-psychological sense, and all organisms qualify as agents, whether in their routine interactions with the environment or conspecifics, or, depending on the account, in certain internal processes such as development. What defines a system as agential is its tendency to reach a goal—that is, a stable endpoint—across a wide range of circumstances. The notion of goal-directedness and its application to biological processes has faced strong criticism for being either superfluous—merely a reformulation of adaptation, and therefore reducible to natural selection—or an unwarranted extension of a psychological concept to a non-psychological domain (DiFrisco and Gawne 2025). Furthermore, this notion leads to an unclear stance on whether, in its application to development, agency is conceived as a heuristic tool, or manner of speaking, or as an actual attribution, particularly in the case of evolution (Potter and Mitchell 2024).

On the other hand, making NC a necessarily agential process risks tying it to particular accounts of agency for which there is no wide consensus, since such a presupposition is not shared throughout the literature and different accounts of agency—even within the goal-directedness view of agency—differ widely in scope, making the boundaries of NC even fuzzier.

In our talk, we will examine the concept of Constitutive NC, tracing how development has become discursively linked to Niche Construction over time, and how this inclusion has been argued for and applied in recent works. Following such literature, we shall then present the argument that incorporating development as NC requires treating development as tied to agency understood as goal-directedness. Finally, we will delve into some of the issues that follow from considering phenotypic changes as NC, especially the fact that it leads to understanding Niche Construction in general as an agential process and that it worsens several of the problems NC already faced prior to the incorporation of Constitutive NC, namely its *ubiquity* and *holism*. Such problems, we argue, are aggravated by the lack of any kind of “relevance threshold” with which to discriminate cases

of very minimal changes to environmental factors—with no, or virtually no, translation in terms of evolutionary pressures—from other cases with clear potential evolutionary consequences, what has been called “universal NC.” Incorporating development as Niche Construction without such a threshold is a step toward rendering NC so expansive that it becomes coextensive with life itself.

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Modal Transcendentalism without Transcendental Idealism?

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Abstract

The main thesis I aim to defend is that modal transcendentalism is incompatible with transcendental idealism. In what follows, I will explain what this thesis consists in, motivate its importance, and outline the argumentative strategy I will pursue in support of it.

Modal transcendentalism is a new theory of metaphysical modality developed by Jessica Leech in her book *Thinking of Necessity: A Kantian Account of Modal Thought and Modal Metaphysics*. It is a Kant-inspired theory according to which:

1. Metaphysical necessity is the strictest real necessity.
2. p is objectively necessary if and only if p follows with logical necessity from some conditions of objectivity (or of objective thought).
3. Metaphysical necessity is objective necessity.

For Leech, then, metaphysical necessity is not an absolute necessity (against what is perhaps the majority view, she holds that absolute necessity is logical necessity rather than metaphysical necessity) but rather a necessity relative to the conditions of objectivity.

Leech introduces the conditions of objectivity as a response to the problem of reality (adopting at this point the terminology and exposition of Gardner (1999)). This problem, which lies at the foundation of Kant's Copernican turn, concerns the relation between mind and world: what is the relation between mind and world such that our mental states are, or can be, about the world? If we assume that the objects of the world are absolutely mind-independent, we cannot give a satisfactory answer to this question. That is why Leech, following Kant, proposes as a solution the idea that the objects of the world are not absolutely mind-independent but must conform to the conditions of objectivity.

Now, what are these conditions of objectivity, and what is their source? For Kant, as he explains in the *Critique of Pure Reason*, these conditions are the a priori forms of sensibility (every object of experience must be in space and time) and the a priori forms of the understanding (the twelve categories; for example: every object of experience must

be subject to causal relations). Moreover, according to Kant, the source of these conditions lies in the subject, and the objects of experience (phenomena) exhibit these conditions insofar as they are subject to the conditions imposed by the subject. This explanation lies at the foundation of his doctrine of transcendental idealism.

Does Leech accept this explanation? Her position with respect to this Kantian doctrine is, in my view, not entirely clear. However, taking into account both the book cited above and other earlier works (especially Leech (2011)), I think her stance can be reconstructed as follows:

1. Without committing herself to accepting all the conditions of objectivity that Kant lists, she finds some of them plausible.
2. Without committing herself to accepting transcendental idealism as an explanation of the source of the conditions of objectivity, she finds it a plausible explanation.

Moreover, something Leech acknowledges is that some explanation of the source of the conditions of objectivity must be given—one that allows us to maintain that objective necessity is the strictest real necessity and, therefore, metaphysical necessity. Hence the importance of the main thesis I aim to defend. The principal consequence is that if modal transcendentalism implies transcendental idealism, then Leech's theory is inconsistent; and if it does not imply it, this Kant-inspired theory of modality should offer a non-Kantian explanation of the source of the conditions of objectivity that satisfies the requirement above.

The argumentative strategy I will follow to defend my main thesis is as follows. I will take as my starting point an objection to modal transcendentalism that Leech herself considers: objective necessity is not the strictest real necessity since it only concerns the reality about which we can think objectively (phenomenal reality); there is a type of necessity that is stricter because it encompasses all of reality independently of our capacity for representation. What I will try to show is that transcendental idealism cannot respond satisfactorily to this objection.

A methodological problem my argument faces is that there is no consensus among scholars either about the exact meaning of the doctrine of transcendental idealism or about how it should be interpreted. Since my aim is not to resolve those interpretive disputes, I will proceed as follows. Following Allais (2004), I will accept that transcendental idealism is a position with three central components:

1. Kant's distinction between phenomena and things in themselves.
2. Kant's idealism: phenomena are, in some sense and to some degree, dependent on our minds.
3. Kant's humility: we cannot have knowledge of things in themselves.

I will consider the three main interpretive lines that have been proposed for this doctrine (Rohlf (2024)): the two-objects interpretation, the two-aspects interpretation in its

metaphysical version, and the two-aspects interpretation in its epistemological version. My argument will attempt to show that none of the three interpretations can respond satisfactorily to the objection raised above.

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Affective Disclosure and the Roots of Epistemic Commitment: A Response to Álvarez-González’s “Emotional Phenomenology: A New Puzzle”

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Abstract

Álvarez-González’s “Emotional Phenomenology: A New Puzzle” (2025) poses a genuine and carefully articulated problem: if emotional phenomenology cannot be treated dogmatically in the way perceptual phenomenology can, how can the guiding role of emotion in action and evaluative thought be rational? The Puzzle highlights a fundamental tension in emotional experience: emotions appear simultaneously dogmatic (compelling and action-guiding) and hypothetical (epistemically open and in need of further justification). His proposed solution—that emotional phenomenology *presents-as-worth-attending-relative-to-a-specific-meaning* its contents and is therefore epistemically hypothetical though practically dogmatic—represents an important contribution to the practical and motivational role of emotion. This paper, however, argues that although the puzzle exists it doesn’t necessarily imply a flawed epistemological role for emotions. Drawing on recent work in the epistemology of perceptual salience and on the phenomenology of affective-cognitive experience, I argue that the epistemic character of perceptual commitment is not a purely cognitive feature and is not exclusive of perceptual phenomenology. It is, rather, grounded in an affective-discriminatory sensitivity that is structurally continuous with emotional experience. Once this is recognized, the asymmetry between emotional and perceptual phenomenology on which Álvarez-González’s puzzle depends significantly weakens, and a stronger epistemological role for emotion becomes available—one that does not require assimilating it to perception but refuses to render it merely hypothetical.

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Practical Moral Expertise and Skill

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Abstract

“Moral expertise” can be understood in various ways, but broadly speaking, it is understood as either a kind of theoretical expertise, a kind of practical expertise, or a combination thereof (Bina, Bonicalzi, and Croce, 2024). Alongside this broader debate about how moral expertise is best understood, philosophers have devoted special attention to practical moral expertise, advancing several distinct accounts of its nature. Driver (2013), for example, characterises a practical moral expert as someone “who acts morally better than others” (p. 283)—typically in comparison with ‘normally performing adults’ (p. 284). A recent proposal is offered by Shepherd (2022), who develops an account of practical moral expertise in terms of skill. Shepherd’s aim is to investigate “moral skill”, roughly understood as the capacity for morally excellent behaviour.

Broadly speaking, Shepherd (2022) argues that human agents cannot acquire a capacity for morally excellent behaviour across all domains of human life—what he calls *global moral skill*. Based on empirical accounts of skill acquisition, he holds that human agents do not have the psychological resources to develop this kind of capacity. Instead, agents can at best develop *local moral skill*: a more limited capacity that enables morally excellent behaviour within particular domains, such as domains associated with specific social roles (for example, being a father). Moreover, Shepherd maintains that local moral skill is precarious because it is “prone to misfire” (p. 729). One reason for this is that “moral excellence does not easily transfer” (p. 728) across domains. Given that everyday life confronts us with a wide variety of situations involving different moral considerations, it is therefore easy to encounter circumstances that exceed the limits of one’s local moral skill. A further source of precariousness is that agents “often lack the time and the wherewithal to practice shifting between” (p. 728) different agential modes as circumstances change. As a result, agents may be uncertain about how to appropriately approach a situation—for example, whether to respond as a friend or as a teacher when a student is facing personal difficulties—thereby increasing the likelihood that local moral skill will misfire. Shepherd’s conclusion, then, is that moral skill is “limited in scope, and precarious” (p. 713).

The central claim of this talk is that Shepherd’s own account of skill, as developed in *The Shape of Agency: Control, Action, Skill, Knowledge* (2021), supports a more complex picture of moral skill than he allows. To defend this claim, based on Shepherd’s (2021)

general account of skill, I propose a third alternative of moral skill, “mid-level moral skill”, which is less demanding than global moral skill but broader in scope than local moral skill. If my claim is correct, this would entail that framing moral skill exclusively in terms of global or local moral skill risks overlooking alternative perspectives that might lead to a more nuanced conclusion than Shepherd’s (2022) characterisation of moral skill as limited and precarious.

I then illustrate the significance of this revised framework by considering a more fundamental methodological worry: whether it is appropriate to investigate practical moral expertise by relying on philosophical and empirical accounts of skill. I argue that these accounts can help us make progress toward a better characterisation of practical moral expertise by assessing the practical possibilities of different models of it. With appropriate qualifications in place, this is clearly illustrated by Shepherd’s (2022) account. At the same time, I suggest that we should be cautious of introducing assumptions into our understanding of practical moral expertise that may be unproblematic in the case of non-moral skills but problematic in the moral case. In particular, I focus on the idea of *success*, and argue that importing this idea from general theories of skill into the moral domain can lead us to underestimate the significance of being rightly motivated when acting morally. As a result, this allows for cases where someone can be both a moral hypocrite and a practical moral expert.

The talk concludes by suggesting two ways of addressing this worry: either by understanding moral skill as a necessary but not sufficient condition for practical moral expertise, or by adopting a more robust conception of moral action—one that builds appropriate motivation into its success conditions.

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The Relevant and the Irrelevant: Against Truthmaker Necessitarianism

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Abstract

In this paper, I present four arguments against truthmaker necessitarianism, the thesis according to which if T makes $\langle P \rangle$ true, then it is impossible for T to exist and for $\langle P \rangle$ to be false. Truthmaker theorists (e.g., Armstrong (2004); Cameron (2008); (2013, p. 462); Rodriguez-Pereyra (2006); (2008, p. 10)) generally take it for granted that the truthmaker necessitates the truth, and few reject it (see, e.g., Heil (2000), Parsons (1999), Stenwall (2016; 2017)). I show that truthmaker necessitarianism runs into four problems, and that we should reject it in favor of truthmaker contingentism (the rejection of truthmaker necessitarianism).

The first problem concerns exclusion. For a truthmaker to necessitate a proposition, it has to exclude relevant entities that would have made that proposition false. For instance, the counterfactual

\langle Had Jane dropped the mug, it would have broken \rangle

could be false in another possible world where there is a pillow on the ground underneath the mug. The truthmaker for this counterfactual must necessitate that there is no pillow there. But the truthmaker does not have to exclude that there is a book on the ground underneath the mug, since even if there were a book, the mug would have broken had Jane dropped it. The truthmaker does not have to exclude that the floor is crooked either, since had Jane dropped the mug, it would still have broken. However, in another possible world, there is a book on the ground underneath the mug and the floor is crooked but had Jane dropped the mug, it would not have broken, since in this case, it would be the right conditions for the mug not to break. The truthmaker necessitarianist has to explain what entities are relevant in every case.

The second problem is that the truthmaker necessitarianist has to provide an infinite number of truthmakers for each counterfactual. She can take the truthmaker for the counterfactual above to consist in natural laws, the mug's fragility, an entity that excludes a book underneath the mug. But she could equally posit a truthmaker that instead excludes the floor's being crooked. Similarly, there are many relevant entities that together

are sufficient but neither is necessary to make the counterfactual false, and the necessitarianist can posit a truthmaker to exclude one entity and not the other. Since it is an arbitrary choice, the necessitarianist has to posit that every counterfactual has an infinite number of truthmakers.

The third problem is an epistemic problem. Let us assume that there are entities that exclude things like pillows, books, etc. Still, what does the truthmaker for every counterfactual consist in? The question for the necessitarianist is to say what entities each truthmaker for a counterfactual consists in. Given that they have to include an infinite number of entities and given that deciding what relevant entities are is problematic, the necessitarianist cannot state what each truthmaker for each counterfactual is. The truthmaker contingentist does not face this problem as she does not posit truthmakers that exclude relevant entities.

The fourth problem is an infinite regress that faces the necessitarianist. Since the necessitarianist has to exclude either the book (call it *A*) or the floor's being crooked (call it *B*), then, on her account, had *A* and *B* been the case then:

⟨Had *A* and *B* been the case, *R* would not have been the case⟩

(where ⟨*R*⟩ is ⟨Had Jane dropped the mug, it would have broken⟩). But this is a new counterfactual and the necessitarianist has to provide a necessitating truthmaker for it. We can repeat the same thing for the new counterfactual. This implies that every time the necessitarianist provides a truthmaker for a counterfactual, she has to provide truthmakers for an infinite number of counterfactuals. The truthmaker contingentist does not face this problem as she does not posit necessitating truthmakers. Of course she can provide truthmakers for all these counterfactuals, but this is not a result of her commitment and she does not have to do this every time she provides a truthmaker for a counterfactual.

Given this, we should reject necessitation from our truthmaker theories and adopt a grounding-first approach, where we only look for what grounds each truth and that it is. We do not have to look for what necessitates. Doing so means avoiding all the above problems and having an easier time providing truthmakers for different kinds of truths.

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A Matter of Attitude? Two Senses of “Expressive” in Expressivism

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Abstract

Two main families of expressivist theories can be found in the literature. On the one hand, Robert Brandom’s expressivism about logical vocabulary (extended also to modal, epistemic, and normative vocabularies) is grounded in inference (Brandom, 1994; Brandom & Hlobil, 2024). According to inferentialism, conceptual content is articulated inferentially. Expressive terms make explicit the inferential commitments of speakers. For instance, when I use a conditional, I express my commitment to the material inference from the antecedent to the consequent. On this account, expressive vocabulary expresses higher-order concepts: they do not contribute to the propositional or conceptual content that they take as argument but perform a different role in communication. Let’s call this branch of expressivism *Higher-Order expressivism* (HO).

On the other hand, a different use of “expressive” originates in metaethics, going back to Ayer (1936) and Stevenson (1937). On this view, moral vocabulary expresses the speaker’s (non-cognitive) attitudes, so that moral utterances are not straightforwardly propositional, in contrast with descriptive uses of language. Contemporary metaethical expressivism has refined this claim in order to deal with the Frege-Geach problem, which concerns the embedding of moral sentences in truth-functional contexts. The result is more sophisticated versions of metaethical expressivism, which aim at both accounting for the propositional and truth-related behavior of normative claims and at preserving their distinctively attitudinal character. Let’s refer to this family of theories as *Attitude-Based expressivism* (ABE).

Some authors have argued that these two forms of expressivism, although of different origins, are compatible (Price, 2011; Incurvati and Schlöder, 2024). Recently, Incurvati and Schlöder have defended an inferentialist form of expressivism about logic and other vocabularies (such as modal and moral ones) that seeks to vindicate this compatibility. In this paper, I focus specifically on logical vocabulary, arguing that attempts to reconcile HO and ABE fail to capture its distinctive inferential role. My contention is not to deny that language expresses attitudes, but rather that taking attitude-expression as semantically explanatory reintroduces commitments that inferentialism itself aims to overcome.

As introduced, Incurvati and Schlöder provide an account that seeks to combine an inferentialist view on the individuation of content together with the idea that the semantics of expressive vocabulary are captured by the attitudes they convey. They argue that the meaning of logical vocabulary is determined by the inferential relations between propositions expressed by uses of that vocabulary and the expression of attitudes. For instance: “the semantic value of *not* is given by the inferential relations an assertion or rejection of a sentence containing *not* bear to other assertions or rejections in virtue of the fact that that sentence contains *not*” (Incurvati and Schlöder, 2024, p. 71).

My main concern is that terms such as “expression” and “assertion” introduce an equivocity between the act itself and the result of that act. Taken as acts, the definition incurs a category mistake: the elements of inferences are propositions, not acts. But, if we understand it as the result of those acts, as the propositions expressed, the account becomes uninformative. To illustrate this idea, see this example:

“To wit, from an utterance of *Grass is not green*, which expresses the belief that grass is not green, one can infer the rejection of *Grass is green*, which expresses the disbelief that grass is green” (Incurvati and Schlöder, 2024, p. 70)

On the first reading, there’s a category mistake: one cannot infer an attitude from a content, as those belong to different categories. On the second one, as appealing to relations between contents (inferring “I reject that p ” from “Not p ”), the account collapses into triviality. Both “not p ” and “I reject that p ” fulfil the very same role in the game of giving and asking for reasons. Moreover, this account fails to capture the distinctive role that logical vocabulary performs in an inferentialist framework (and thus, does not succeed in making both accounts compatible): making explicit inferential commitments. Inferentialism revolves around the notion of material inferences, that Brandom takes from Sellars. These inferences are not formal (rather logical validity is built upon them). As such, they do not possess the typical formal constraints common in standard formal languages, such as monotonicity. Much of our reasoning can be defeated by the introduction of new premises. The role of logical vocabulary, on this account, is to make our reasoning explicit, to allow for its critical assessment. This understanding allows for a conception of logic not confined to formal logic, permitting contextualism as non-monotonicity is embraced. I take this to be one of the most valuable contributions of HO.

By contrast, ABE does not provide such resources, at least not initially. Their only option would be to characterize attitudes towards different inferences, but it is unclear how this could be achieved. Since we are dealing with semantics, an account framed in terms of content, and their inferential incompatibilities and consequences, as Brandom provides, seems more adequate.

A positive account of logical expressivism can be built around the central notion of higher-order concepts. Other features usually associated with logical vocabulary—such as their non-descriptive character, or the way they differ from perceptual and empirical vocabulary—derive from this central point. Logical vocabulary, in this sense, belongs to

a family of concepts that includes modal and normative operators: they all take propositions as arguments and have certain roles, such as making explicit inferential relations among them, shifting the circumstances of evaluation or recommending courses of action.

In conclusion, an expressivist account based on the notion of higher-order concept provides a robust explanation of the role of logical vocabulary. Its combination with views that revolve around the expression of attitude introduce difficulties that undermine the inferentialist semantics on which logical expressivism is grounded.

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